

Connection Between Information, Action and Fermat's Least Time Principle?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 6, 2024

We have argued in previous notes that Fermat's least time principle may be linked to p_x from the classical Action = $-Et + p_x x$. One may note that p_x is additive, i.e. one may write $p_1 x + p_2 x$. Given that there is translational invariance in problems using p_x (i.e. reflection, refraction for example), $d/dx p_x = p$ (along x) which is a conserved quantity in a reflection-refraction problem.

In information theory, there exists the notion of information, i.e. $\ln(\text{Probability})$. If one applies this idea to $p_1 x + p_2 x$, i.e. calls p_x information, then $\ln(\text{Prob}) = p_1 x$ constant and one may obtain a probability of $\exp(ip_x)$ if one chooses constant = i . The d/dx derivative of information then yields the conserved quantity p (along x) multiplied by i . We argue that probability is present in a one dimensional reflection-refraction problem and that it is the probability from Shannon's information, namely $\exp(ip_x)$, which is required to solve the problem.

We also consider in this note a situation in which one does not know the form of information as a function of probability, but argues that it is equal to p_x so that d/dx ultimately acts on p_x to yield p (along x), the conserved quantity. We suggest that d/dx information(p_x) should yield p (along x) and ask what form the information should take. We find that $\ln(\text{Prob})$ is a solution. Thus, we suggest that the idea of information is already present in Fermat's least time approach.

Fermat's Least Time Approach

Fermat's least time approach applied to reflection-refraction suggests that a beam in medium n_1 (index of refraction) making an angle with the y axis (surface along x) will refract in medium n_2 (below $y=0$) such that the least amount of time is taken to travel from a point $(0,A)=(x,y)$ to $(x,y=0)$ to $(L-x,A)$. At first this seems like a problem involving time, but time = distance/velocity and so one has a function of x . An extremization of time actually involves extremization using d/dx (the generator of translation in this translationally invariant problem):

$$d/dx \left\{ \sqrt{A^2 + x^2}/c_1 + \sqrt{A^2 + (L-x)^2}/c_2 \right\} = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \sin(\theta_1)/c_1 = \sin(\theta_2)/c_2 \quad ((1))$$

where θ_1 is the angle of the incident beam with y axis and θ_2 , the refracted. $c_1 = c/n_1$ and $c_2 = c/n_2$.

Furthermore $p_1 = p_{n1}$ and $p_2 = p_{n2}$ so $p(x)_{\text{incident}} = p(x)_{\text{refracted}} \quad ((2))$

i.e. the x component of momentum is conserved.

A simpler way of indicating this is to use a piece of the classical action, namely p_x , where p is the x component of momentum. The $d/dx p_x = p$ the conserved momentum along x .

At this point there is no connection with information theory. We point out, however, that:

$P_1x + p_2x$ is the sum of two px pieces. ((3))

Information Theory

The information theory of Shannon defines information as:

Information = $\ln(\text{probability})$ ((4))

In the above reflection-refraction problem, no probability appears explicitly, but there is probability in the problem because a single photon either reflects or refracts. We will discuss the presence of this probability in more detail later when we consider one dimensional reflection-refraction.

If one were to link ((4)) with ((3)) one might suggest that:

Probability = $\exp(ipx)$ ((5))

where i is used to create periodicity because one does not want probability growing or shrinking indefinitely.

It might seem that ((5)) is forcing a probability into the reflection-refraction picture, but a one dimensional reflection-refraction problem shows that it is actually present and that ((5)) is in fact the form of probability needed to solve the problem. If one considers a photon with momentum p and velocity c (hence $E=pc$) moving in the positive x direction hitting an interface along the y axis at $x=0$ with n_2 (index of refraction) for $x>0$, then one requires two equations to solve for the probability to reflect and refract assuming an incident probability of 1. If one uses $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability, one may consider this and its first derivative to be continuous at $x=0$ i.e.

$A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip_2x)$ at $x=0$ for $A=1$ and

$Ap \exp(ipx) - Bp \exp(-ipx) = C p_2 \exp(ip_2x)$ at $x=0$ for $A=1$ ((6))

((6)) may be solved for B and C and then BB/c and CC/c_2 represent classical probabilities to reflect and refract because BB and CC represent fluxes. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ is a kind of square root flux which is not exactly a probability, but seems to represent nevertheless the probability in Shannon's information.

We note that the two equations of ((6)) may be combined (by dividing). If one considers the right and left hand sides of the first equation of ((6)) to be $P(x<0)$ and $P(x>0)$, then one has:

$d/dx \ln(P(x<0)) = d/dx \ln(P(x>0))$ at $x=0$ ((7))

Deducing the Form of Shannon's Information

We consider the problem of reflection-refraction and ask whether one may deduce the form of Shannon's information. We argue that px is a relevant argument from Fermat's least principle, so we suggest that:

$$\text{Probability}(px) \text{ and } \text{Information}(px) = px \quad ((8))$$

Then $d/dx \text{Information}(px) = p(\text{along } x)$, i.e. the conserved quantity ((9))

Let $G(P(px)) = \text{information}$, where G is an unknown function of Probability $P(px)$. Then:

$$d/dx G(P) = p \quad \text{Let } y=px, \text{ so } dG/dP dP/dy p = p \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{Thus: } dG/dP = 1/dP/dy$$

$$\text{A solution is: } P=\exp(y) \text{ where } y=px \text{ with } G = \ln(P) \quad ((11))$$

One may modify this so that one has $\exp(iy)$ instead of $\exp(y)$.

Thus, one obtains the form $\ln(P)$ for information from considerations of Fermat's Least Time principle, which is linked with the px piece of the classical action $-Et+px$. Formally, $-Et+px$ is the relativistic and nonrelativistic action of a particle i.e. $A = -m_0 \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $A = .5mvv t$ with $v=x/t$. We assume the same form $-Et+px$ for a photon.

Conclusion

We try to show that Shannon's form for information, namely $\ln(\text{probability})$ follows from Fermat's Least Time Principle. We argue that minimizing time really leads to $d/dx \text{Function}(x)=0$ and that this, in turn, yields $p(\text{along } x) \text{ incident} = p(\text{along } x) \text{ refracted}$, i.e. one has a conservation equation in $p(\text{along } x)$ i.e. momentum along x . This suggests the function px as being key because $d/dx px = p$.

Shannon defined the function information as $\ln(\text{Probability})$. In the Fermat's least time picture, it may seem that there is no probability. We suggest that one consider p_1x+p_2x and apply $\ln(\text{Probability})$. This implies that probability = $\exp(ipx)$ if one wishes to have a periodic function instead of growing or shrinking one. Thus, $\ln(\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)) = ip_1x+ip_2x$.

We suggest that probability is in fact key to the reflection-refraction problem. If one considers such a problem in one dimension, then there is a probability to reflect and one to refract. We try to apply the probability $\exp(ipx)$ to such a problem and find that it may be solved by making $\exp(ipx)$ and its first derivative continuous at $x=0$. These two conditions combined lead to $d/dx \ln(\text{Probability } x<0) = d/dx \ln(\text{Probability } x>0)$ evaluated at $x=0$. The probability $\exp(ipx)$ is not the classical probability, but it does seem to be linked to Shannon's information and solves the reflection-refraction problem. One may obtain classical probabilities from the weights squared of

the various $\exp(ipx)$ s. The actual Shannon's probability in a reflection-refraction problem actually involves interference. Thus, for $x < 0$, Shannon's probability is $A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx)$ while for $x > 0$, Shannon's probability is $C\exp(ip2x)$ where $p_2 = n_2 p$ and $n_1 = 1$ so $p_1 = p$.

Finally, we try to deduce the form of Shannon's information from the refraction-reflection problem. We suggest that $P(px)$ and that $\text{information} = px$ so $d/dx \text{Information} = p$. This leads to $\text{Information} = \ln(\text{probability})$ as a possible solution. In other words, the notion of information seems to follow from Fermat's Least Time Principle.